

Consumer Preference on Internet Marketing -A Study

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Abstract

Internet marketing refers to promotion and selling hard work that utilizes the Web and email to compel straight sales via electronic commerce, in accumulation to sales leads from websites or emails. Internet selling and online advertising pains are generally used in combination with conventional types of publicity such as broadcasting, small screen, the media, and magazines. In this process of learning, we are trying to explore the mindset of youth towards internet marketing. Find out what products do youth purchase through internet marketing and try to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of internet marketing. Significance of the study is to see further how to develop internet marketing and thereby satisfying the customers. Data collection for the current study is done through Google forms developed by the researcher, which was circulated among the youth. Collected data were analyzed using graphical representation and simple statistics, namely percentage.

Keywords: Consumer preference, Internet marketing.

Introduction

Consumer preference is as the personal tastes of the human being who are customers, considered by their contentment with individual's objects after they've purchased them. This fulfillment is referred to as usefulness. Purchaser importance can be brave by how end- user effectiveness compares between unusual things.

Internet marketing refers to publicity and promotion hard work to utilize the Web and email to constrain straight sales via an electronic exchange, in adding up to sales leads as of websites or emails.

Factors Influencing Consumer Preference

- Cost
- Consumer income
- Available substitutes
- Advertising
- Social institutions
- Consumer accessibility

How to Determine Consumer Preference?

To determine what consumer prefers, you have to give them similar products to compare. When giving them two or more products to compare, each product should be in equal amount. For example, you are asking a person to compare apple with oranges is reasonable, but

asking them to compare six apples with two oranges is not fair. One preference that doesn't change when evaluating commodities is that consumers always prefer more to less.

Types of Internet Marketing:

- **Search Engine Marketing (SEM) & Pay-Per-Click advertising (PPC)**

SEM (Search Engine Marketing) is the procedure of fast website interchange by purchasing ads on exploration engines. Google AdWords is by many methods the most accepted paid search policy used by investigative marketers, followed by Bing Ads. Beyond that, there are several “2nd tier PPC platforms” as well as PPC (Digital Marketing: The 7 Different Types of Online Marketing <https://webstrategies.com/digital-marketing-7-different-types/>) publicity options on the major social networks.

Typically, SEM and PPC advertising are approved out during search engines, which charge advertisers a programmed amount every time their ads are clicked. While the search engines profit considerably from this model, site owners promote from being able to aim their impending customers accurately.

- **Content Marketing**

According to the Content Marketing Institute, content marketing is “a premeditated marketing approach paying attention to creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and dependable content to attract and retain a clearly-defined audience — and, ultimately, to drive profitable customer action.” (Digital Marketing: The 7 Different Types of Online marketing <https://webstrategies.com/digital-marketing-7-different-types/>)

- **Social media marketing**

As an end- user, many people already know a lot about social media, but their information about social media marketing is naturally more limited. If companies can create social media content that provides value to others, they can successfully connect with clientele. (Digital Marketing: The 7 Different Types of Online Marketing <https://webstrategies.com/digital-marketing-7-different-types/>)

- **Affiliate marketing**

Affiliate marketing is the process of earning a payment by promoting other people, or company's goods. You find a product you like, promote it to others (usually through your blog), and earn a piece of the profit for each sale that you make. (Digital Marketing: The 7 Different Types of Online Marketing <https://webstrategies.com/digital-marketing-7-different-types/>)

- **Email marketing**

Email marketing has long been a pillar for any selling attempting to generate sales via the internet. It provides direct contact with clients and allows you to drive probable customers to your website. In a few simple steps, you can provide updates, exciting news, reminders, etc. to your customers in a matter of minutes. At the same time, you can use these newsletters as printable, direct mail pieces or even flyers. (Digital Marketing: The 7 Different Types of Online marketing <https://webstrategies.com/digital-marketing-7-different-types/>)

Advantages of Internet Marketing

- Shallow risk
- Reduction in cost through automation and use of electronic media
- Faster response to both marketers and the end- user
- Increased ability to measure and collect data
- Opens the possibility to a market of one through personalization
- Increased interactivity

- Increased exposure to products and services
 - Boundless universal accessibility
- (Advantages and disadvantages of Digital Marketing ... <https://sinansoft.com/blog/advantages-and-disadvantages-ofdigital-marketing/>)

Disadvantages of Internet Marketing

- Dependability on technology
- Security, privacy issues
- Maintenance cost due to the constantly evolving environment
- Higher transparency of pricing, and increased price competition
- Worldwide competition through globalization.

(Advantages and disadvantages of Digital Marketing ...<https://sinansoft.com/blog/advantages-and-disadvantages-ofdigital-marketing/>)

Specialized Areas of Internet Marketing

- Internet marketing can also be broken down into more specialized areas such as Web marketing, email marketing, and social media marketing:
- Web marketing includes e-commerce Web sites, affiliate marketing Web sites, promotional or informative Web sites, online advertising on search engines, and organic search engine results via search engine optimization (SEO).
- Email marketing involves both advertising and promotional marketing efforts via e-mail messages to current and prospective customers.
- Social media marketing involves both advertising and marketing (including viral marketing) efforts via social networking sites like Face book, Twitter, YouTube and Digg.
- Search Engine Optimization (SEO) involves the optimization of landing pages within your website to increase the number of visitors.

(What is Internet Marketing? Webopedia Definition https://www.webopedia.com/TERM/I/internet_marketing.html)

Need for the study

The researcher, having gone through several reviews relating to the current research, felt that there is a great need to study about the consumer preference on internet marketing. As we are aware that these days, youth are more in internet marketing rather than direct physical marketing. Hence the researcher wanted to find out what products do youth purchase through internet marketing and try to investigate the reward and disadvantages of internet marketing through this study.

Significance of the study is to see further how to develop internet marketing and thereby to satisfy the customers.

Objectives

- To find out if youth are aware of internet marketing.
- To assess what products the customers prefer to purchase through internet marketing.
- To analyze the customer satisfaction and
- To evaluate further how to develop internet marketing.

Methodology

Sample selection: A total number of 103 samples were randomly selected for the current research based on their willingness to respond to the Google form. The researcher developed ten items scale

to measure the consumer preference on internet marketing, which was formulated in the type of Google forms and administrated online to the respondents. The data thus collected was analyzed using graphical representation and simple statistics, namely percentage.

Results and discussion

Fig.1 Pie chart showing the distribution of respondents based on gender.

Fig.2 Pie chart showing the awareness level among respondents.

It can be observed from the above fig. 2 that 86.4% of the respondents are aware of internet marketing.

What Products were Advertised Online?

The following are the reactions received relating to the products marketed online by the Respondents:

Food

Phone

Shoes, bags, watches

A - Z

Cosmetics, books, dress,

Electronic products, online courses, etc

Dress

Ornaments, electrical appliances

Cosmetics

Groceries, books, etc

Portrait

Accessories and cosmetics

Devices etc

Watches, mobiles.

Stationery products, Home appliances

Perfume

Fabrics.

Medicines, luxury and premium goods

Grocery,

Shoes, toys

Products which r available in offline stores and even which r not available in offline stores r marketed in online markets

Commercial Products

Cooking products

Groceries and beauty products

Consumer products

Consumer goods, durable goods, from pin to ship

What Products do you Purchase through Online Marketing?

The responses received relating to the products purchased through online marketing are quite similar to that of the responses given above.

Fig 3 Pie chart shows the proportion of respondents who were contented with e-marketing

From the above fig 3, it is observed that 77.7% of the respondents are satisfied with internet marketing.

Reasons why respondents are satisfied with internet marketing are as follows

Quality brand

Low- cost Efficiency Quick transaction Easy online payment Warranty

Repayment option, no need to stand in line, time- consuming

More comfortable

Home delivery

Trusted brands Affordable price

Consumes less time No need to go to the shop directly Availability of information regarding products Goods return policy delivered at doorstep

Reasons why respondents are not satisfied with internet marketing are as follows

1. Products won't last long, 2. They are somewhat local, 3. Late delivery, 4. Differential products Showing is one and delivered another one, 5. Return is irregular.

Fig 4 Pie chart showing how frequently customers shop online

From the above figure, we observe that majority of the respondents i.e. 71% of them buy quarterly. 5% of them buy weekly.

What more services do you hope from e-marketing?

The following are the services that respondents hope from online marketing:

Less money for better marketing

Quality

I expect the exact product of a delivery

Delivery should be quick.

Discounts

Need quick delivery in remote areas Debit card offers to all Banks

More employment opportunities

It must be user-friendly.

Better customer service, fast delivery

1. Easy delivery 2. No second-hand products 3. Freshly new ones should be provided

Less expensive free delivery right products

Improvement in the quality of products

Sales at a cheaper rate

Easy returning correct size measurement for clothes and shoes Quick delivery

Perfect security in payment

Safe packaging

Perfect fit for the dresses Durability of the goods Delivery condition should be the same as in the demo pictures

Give suggestions to improve e-marketing?

The suggestions received from the respondents regarding improvement in e-marketing are as follows:

Can have more collections

Easy accessibility Fast transportation

Suggest the better offers

Customer service has to be improved

The e-marketing agent should check the supplier...so customers get a good product

Discounts, offers, Best customer care, Customer service

Recruiting more employees with sufficient pay, Quick response to the returned good

It should spread across rural and village areas, Easy return

Give more offers for weekend sale; they can connect with their customer online. They can consider consumer grievances.

Can also provide the negative aspects of the commodities

Delivery time to be more accurate *Phone talks with human rather than speaking with a machine, Built a loyal customer base and analyzed the customer and sell the product through e-marketing.

Have a forever lasting first impression Create social media graphics Realities of bloggers should be understood Connect with employees online Have a good rapport with customers and employees

Give more details about the product which should be right because sometimes the product features are different.

Cash on delivery with a choice of selection and exchange facilities will enhance the sale of products.

Track the location where the delivery is, as soon as possible.

Conclusion

- The majority (86.4%) of the respondents are aware of internet marketing.
- Customers prefer to purchase (A-Z) all the products essential for livelihood purpose through internet marketing.
- Most of the customers are satisfied because of Quality brand, Low- cost efficiency, Quick transaction, Easy online payment etc.
- Some of the suggestions put forth to evaluate further how to develop internet marketing are Easy accessibility, Fast transportation, Suggest the better offers, Have a forever lasting first impression etc.

Suggestions and Implication

From the above study, we come to know that internet marketing is good, but from some individual point of view, it is not. The primary thing to be changed is to avoid poor contact with the customer and to have direct communication with the customer, which will increase the usage of internet marketing. Secondly, internet marketing does not cover the rural areas; hence, many people in rural areas are not aware of using internet marketing. To avoid; this they should cover rural areas where they can reach more people; this will increase usage of internet marketing.

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